

iPlan Gov: A Smart Analytics System for Decision-Support in Local Government Planning and Development

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ABSTRACT:

This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate iPlan Gov, a localized, analytics-driven decision-support framework and digital system for the Planning and Development Office (PDO) of a Local Government Unit (LGU) in Nueva Ecija, developed in response to the contextual planning and governance needs of Philippine LGUs. Using a descriptive-developmental research design, 14 respondents assessed the system's technical quality, usability, acceptability, and effectiveness based on ISO 9126 software quality standards. Assessment of the existing planning process revealed strong institutional coordination, defined staff roles, and effective planning practices; however, gaps persisted in workflow consistency, project monitoring, data accuracy, inter-office collaboration, and integration of multiple information sources. Although digital tools were already utilized, limitations in standardization and user confidence highlighted the need for a unified, analytics-driven decision-support system tailored to local governance processes. The development of iPlan Gov followed Agile methodology, emphasizing iterative development, user-centered design, stakeholder feedback, and continuous testing. The system embodies the study's primary contribution by integrating analytics-based dashboards, automated reporting, and decision-support mechanisms aligned with Philippine LGU planning workflows. An estimated project cost of ₱4,747,000 was identified for the proposed implementation, covering hardware, software, and technical services, with projected maintenance provisions to support long-term usability and system reliability. Evaluation results indicated that IT experts rated the system highly in terms of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability, while end-users confirmed its effectiveness in data management, performance monitoring, transparency,

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and evidence-based decision-making. As a whole, iPlan Gov system offers a replicable, user-centered, and analytics-driven digital governance framework that enhances planning efficiency, strengthens accountability, and supports data-informed decision-making among Philippine LGUs.

Keywords: Digital Governance System, Evidence-Based Decision Making, iPlan Gov, ISO 9126, Planning and Development Office.

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INTRODUCTION

Local Government Units (LGUs) in the Philippines serve as the frontline of governance, responsible for implementing programs, delivering services, and promoting socio-economic development within their jurisdictions [1]. At the heart of LGU operations is the Planning and Development Office (PDO), which is tasked with preparing development plans, conducting research, monitoring projects, and ensuring that local initiatives align with both national policies and the community's needs [2,3]. Despite this central role, many PDOs in the Philippines still rely heavily on manual processes, fragmented information systems, and traditional reporting mechanisms, resulting in delays in planning outputs, compromised data quality, and challenges in evidence-based decision-making [4,5]. This situation is evident in one municipality of Nueva Ecija, where planning unit continues to struggle with disconnected data sources, labor-intensive consolidation of Comprehensive Land Use Plan (CLUP), Comprehensive Development Plan (CDP), Local Development Investment Program (LDIP), and the Annual Investment Program (AIP) documents, and slow generation of monitoring reports. These localized challenges hinder the PDO's ability to produce timely, accurate, and actionable planning outputs, thereby limiting the effectiveness of local development initiatives.

The Philippine government has increasingly recognized the need for digital transformation in local governance, emphasizing e-governance and data-driven decision-making to improve efficiency, transparency, and accountability [5,6,7]. By integrating data analytics into LGU operations, PDOs can extract actionable insights from raw data, detect trends, anticipate future needs, and enhance the reliability of development plans [8,9]. This approach aligns with initiatives such as eGovPH and other national programs promoting digitalization of public services.

In the recent years, the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG), and the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) have introduced several digital systems intended to support local governance modernization [10]. DILG initiatives include the Barangay Information Governance System (BIGS), which provides barangays with tools for data management, planning, and governance reporting [11]; the Electronic Business One-Stop Shop (e-BOSS), which streamlines business permitting and licensing in collaboration with DICT [12]; and the Local Governance Performance Management System (LGPMS), an online platform that tracks LGU performance. Meanwhile, DICT's eGovPH Super App integrates a wide range of transactional government services and has supported millions of users and transactions nationwide [13].

While these systems improve specific governance functions, they do not directly address the internal planning workflow, cross-department data integration, or analytics-driven monitoring processes required by municipal PDOs. Existing national platforms are largely designed for reporting, compliance, or sector-specific services, rather than for synchronizing local planning documents, automating investment programming, or consolidating real-time project monitoring data. This gap underscores the need for a localized framework that strengthens the internal planning ecosystem of municipalities, particularly those experiencing persistent fragmentation in planning processes.

However, LGUs in the Philippines vary widely in terms of resources, infrastructure, and technical capacity, requiring a context-specific framework that can guide digital transformation while addressing local constraints [14,15,16]. Some urban centers possess robust ICT infrastructure,

skilled staff, and advanced data systems, while smaller or remote LGUs often struggle with connectivity, budget limitations, and human resource challenges, creating a digital divide that affects planning efficiency and transparency.

This study is therefore motivated by the need to develop an Integrated Analytics-Driven Digital Systems Framework tailored for Philippine LGUs. The framework aims to improve the planning and development functions of PDOs by enhancing efficiency, data accuracy, and transparency [8,17]. By leveraging analytics, it envisions real-time monitoring of projects, predictive planning for investments, integration of multiple data sources, and improved stakeholder engagement, all adapted to the unique conditions of the Philippine setting. Ultimately, this framework seeks to support LGUs in adopting sustainable, evidence-based, and technologically-enabled planning processes that strengthen local governance and contribute to national development objectives [15,16].

Research Problems

This study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How may the current operations of the Planning and Development Office (PDO) be described in terms of:

1.1 current planning processes;

1.2 digital practices and tools; and

1.3 operational challenges?

2. How may the Smart Analytics System for Decision-Support in Local Government Planning and Development be designed and developed following the stages of the Agile Model in terms of:

2.1 requirements analysis;

2.2 system design;

2.3 system development;

2.4 testing;

2.5 deployment; and

2.6 maintenance?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed a descriptive–developmental research design, integrating the assessment of existing planning operations with the development and evaluation of a digital decision-support system. Following a quantitative–qualitative–quantitative sequence [18, 19], the study (1) quantitatively assessed current Planning and Development Office (PDO) processes, digital practices, and operational challenges; and (2) utilized qualitative inputs to guide the system design and development using the Agile Model.

The study was conducted at the Planning and Development Office of the LGU in Nueva Ecija, Philippines. Fourteen purposively selected respondents participated: eight PDO personnel and six IT experts. PDO personnel provided operational insights, while IT experts evaluated the system's technical quality. Inclusion criteria required at least six months of relevant experience and direct involvement in planning, data management, or ICT-related functions.

A researcher-developed survey instrument was used to assess the current PDO operations, digital practices, and challenges. Data collection followed a structured process involving literature review, institutional approvals, requirements elicitation, system development using the Agile Model, and system evaluation. Ethical protocols, including informed consent and confidentiality, were strictly observed throughout the study.

Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, and weighted mean, were used to analyze survey data. System quality was interpreted using established verbal descriptors aligned with ISO

9126 criteria. Narrative analysis supported the discussion of system development phases. All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Version 28.

The study complied with RA 10173 (Data Privacy Act of 2012). Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained, and confidentiality was ensured. A formal data-sharing agreement with the LGU authorized the use of planning documents solely for academic and system development purposes.

RESULTS

Current Operations of the Planning and Development Office (PDO)

Table 1 presents the result of the assessment on the current operations of the planning and development office in terms of the following areas: current planning processes, digital practices and tools, and operational challenges.

Table 1. Assessment on the Current Operations of the Planning and Development Office (PDO)

Item Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
Current Planning Processes	3.56	Very Satisfactory
Digital Practices and Tools	3.53	Always
Operational Challenges	3.09	Significant Challenge

As shown in Table 1, the current planning processes of the Planning and Development Office (PDO) were rated very satisfactory ($\bar{x} = 3.56$), indicating that core planning activities are generally well-established and consistently implemented. The use of digital practices and tools was assessed as always ($\bar{x} = 3.53$), reflecting regular reliance on digital technologies in planning tasks. However, operational challenges were still identified as a significant challenge ($\bar{x} = 3.09$), suggesting persistent issues that limit efficiency and support the need for improved, integrated digital solutions.

The Design and Development of the iPlan Gov using Agile Model

The design and development of the *iPlan Gov* system followed the stages of the Agile Model, resulting in a functional, analytics-driven digital planning system aligned with the operational needs of the Planning and Development Office (PDO). The results of each Agile phase are presented to demonstrate how user requirements were translated into system features, architecture, and deployable components.

Requirements Analysis

Results of the requirements analysis revealed that while existing planning processes were generally satisfactory and supported by basic digital tools, the workflow remained fragmented, particularly in handling interrelated planning documents such as the CLUP, CDP, LDIP, and AIP. These findings informed the identification of key system requirements, including document integration, centralized data management, real-time analytics, and automated reporting. To organize development activities and timelines, a Gantt chart was produced.

Figure 1 presents the Gantt chart of activities used to guide the Agile development process.

User interactions and system scope were further defined through a use case analysis, which captured core system functions such as user management, document handling, planning preparation, monitoring, analytics visualization, report generation, audit trails, and data backup.

Figure 2 shows the Use Case Diagram of the *iPlan Gov* system.

Figure 1. Gantt Chart of Activities

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram

System Design

The system design phase resulted in a comprehensive technical blueprint that translated the validated requirements into structured system models. Data flow modeling illustrated how planning data are processed and shared across system modules.

Figure 3 presents the Context Diagram (DFD Level 0) of *iPlan Gov*, illustrating system boundaries and external entities.

Figure 3. Context Diagram of DFD

The logical structure of the system was defined through object-oriented modeling and database design. To support usability and stakeholder validation, user interface mockups were produced, visualizing the dashboard and key system forms.

Figure 4. User Interface Mockups

System Development

Based on the approved design artifacts, the system was implemented as a working prototype integrating front-end and back-end components. Core functionalities for planning document management, analytics visualization, monitoring, and reporting were successfully developed.

Figure 5 shows screenshots of the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) used during system development.

Figure 5. Integrated Development Environment

Testing

System testing results confirmed that the *iPlan Gov* prototype met the identified functional requirements. Test cases covering login, LDIP and AIP creation, viewing, editing, and deletion were successfully executed, with actual results matching expected outcomes.

Table 2 presents sample test cases used to validate system functionality and workflow accuracy.

Table 2. Sample Test Cases

Test Case ID	Module	Test Description	Test Steps	Input Data	Expected Result	Actual Result
TC-001	Login Module	Verify that a user with valid credentials can successfully log in	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Go to login page Enter valid username Enter valid password 	Username: valid user Password: ValidPass123	User is redirected to the dashboard or homepage	User successfully logged in and was redirected to the dashboard
TC-002	LDIP Module	Verify that a user can create a new LDIP record	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Go to LDIP module Click "+" icon Fill out required fields Click "Save" 	Project Name: Sample Project Year: 2026 Budget: 500,000	New LDIP record is saved and displayed in the list	New LDIP record is successfully saved and displayed in the list

TC-003	LDIP Module	Verify that LDIP records are displayed correctly	1. Go to LDIP module 2. Click the view icon in the list of LDIP items	N/A	LDIP records are displayed correctly	LDIP records are displayed correctly
TC-004	LDIP Module	Verify that a user can edit an LDIP record	1. Go to LDIP module 2. Select a record 3. Click the edit icon 4. Click "Update"	Updated Project Name: Sample Project	LDIP record is successfully updated	LDIP record is successfully updated
TC-005	LDIP Module	Verify that a user can delete an LDIP record	1. Go to LDIP module 2. Select a record 3. Click "Delete" 4. Confirm deletion	N/A	Selected record is deleted from the LDIP list	Selected record is deleted from the LDIP list
TC-006	AIP Module	Verify the system allows adding a new AIP entry	1. Go to AIP module 2. Click "+" icon 3. Enter data 4. Save	Program: Health Budget: 300,000	New AIP record created and displayed	New AIP record created and displayed
TC-007	AIP Module	Verify the system displays AIP list	1. Go to AIP module 2. Click the view icon records	N/A	AIP records are displayed	AIP records are displayed
TC-008	AIP Module	Verify editing AIP data works	1. Select AIP record 2. Click Edit icon 3. Edit data 4. Click the Update	Updated Program: Education	AIP record updated	AIP record updated
TC-009	AIP Module	Verify deletion of AIP record	1. Select AIP record 2. Click Delete 3. Confirm	N/A	Record removed	Record removed

Deployment and Cost Analysis

The deployment phase produced a finalized deployment architecture suitable for implementation within the PDO's existing infrastructure.

Figure 6 shows the Deployment Diagram of the *iPlan Gov* system.

Figure 6. Deployment Diagram

Cost analysis results indicated that system implementation requires investments in hardware, software, and services. Hardware costs were estimated at ₱671,000, software costs at ₱4,016,000,

and service-related costs at ₱60,000, resulting in a total projected implementation cost of ₱4,747,000.

Maintenance

The results of system planning include a defined maintenance strategy focusing on system monitoring, updates, troubleshooting, and continuous improvement to ensure long-term reliability, adaptability, and sustained usability of the *iPlan Gov* system.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that while the Planning and Development Office (PDO) demonstrates strong planning processes and an existing use of digital tools, persistent challenges in workflow coordination, data accuracy, standardization, and system integration limit overall efficiency and effectiveness. The development and implementation of the *iPlan Gov* system directly address these gaps by centralizing planning documents, automating workflows, and supporting data-driven decision-making through integrated analytics and reporting tools. Developed using an Agile approach with active stakeholder involvement, *iPlan Gov* was validated by IT experts as technically robust, exhibiting high functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. End-user evaluations further confirmed the system's high acceptability and effectiveness in improving workflow efficiency, transparency, accountability, and informed decision-making. However, the successful and sustainable adoption of the system depends on enabling conditions such as staff digital literacy, organizational support, adequate infrastructure, and continuous training. The study's focus on a single local government unit also suggests the need for caution in generalizing the findings to other contexts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that the PDO, in formal partnership with the NEUST Graduate School, fully adopt and institutionalize the *iPlan Gov* system to centralize planning operations, automate reporting processes, and enhance workflow efficiency. Continuous capacity-building initiatives, with support from the MSIT Program of the NEUST Graduate School, should be implemented to strengthen staff confidence, promote process standardization, and ensure effective utilization of system features, particularly in data integration, dashboard analytics, and decision support. Future studies may expand the scope of implementation by integrating *iPlan Gov* with other municipal offices or higher-level planning systems to improve inter-agency coordination and further strengthen evidence-based governance across broader local and regional contexts.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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